

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING RECITATIVE METHOD TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' VOCABULARY MASTERY

¹Andi Asrifan

²Like Raskova Octaberlina

³Eka Safitri

^{1,3}Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidenreng Rappang

²Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim, Malang, Indonesia

ABSTRACT

The objectives of this research was to find out wheather or not the use of recitative method can improve the students' vocabulary mastery at seventh grade of SMP Negeri 2 Kulo. This research applied a pre-experimental method. The population of the research was the seventh grade students of SMP Negeri 2 Kulo. There were 60 students spread in 3 classes (VII.1, VII.2, and VII.3) and each class consist appropriately 20-21 students. The researcher took cluster sampling and chose VII.2 as the representative and the number of total sample is 19 students. The data were collected by using vocabulary test that consisted 30 items. The result of data analysis showed that there was significant difference of the students' vocabulary mastery after giving treatment by using recitative method. It was proved by the mean score of post-test which was higher than the mean score of pre-test ($73.50 > 49.70$). The researcher found that the p-value was lower than the α ($0.000 < 0,05$), it means that H_1 accepted. Based on the result above, the researcher concludes that the use of recitative method can improves the students' vocabulary mastery.

Keywords: Recitative Method, and Vocabulary

INTRODUCTION

One component of language is vocabulary. Without knowing the meaning of words, the students are unable to read, speak, write and hear. But students can easily read, speak, write and listen by first teaching vocabulary. Vocabulary is a key language feature. The capacity to communicate and communicate our social needs can be defined by providing enough vocabulary. "Vocabulary is one of the important factors for all language learning, as Edward stated in Wahyuni (2012), students should continually learn words while learning structure and practicing sound systems." If the learner has ample vocabulary, he or she would be able to understand the words, speak fluently, and will easily

understand the text's content. Vocabulary is a collection of terms that can be interpreted in a kind of language and useful, in other words a group of words typically described to be understood for the purposes of a sentence. "Vocabulary is the number of words that a person hears, recognizes, understands and uses in speech and writing," says George D. Spache in Fadillah (2011). In other words, Sari's Hornby (2007) describes the phrase "total word number in a language: word list with meaning" "total word number." On the basis of the expert claim, the reseacher will infer that all of the terms used by people in conversation are vocabulary.

For those who learn the language used for listening, speaking, writing and reading, good mastery of vocabulary is important. If the student has adequate vocabulary and the ability to use it correctly, he or she can speak fluently and precisely, write easily or understand what he or she reads or hears. Both skills require a lot of mastery of vocabulary. "The listening, writing, speech and reading skills of students are hampered by their limited vocabulary," Al-Kufaishi said in Fadillah, 2011. In other words, Nation (2011) says that 'In all language skills (i.e., listening, speaking, reading, and writing) vocabulary articles play a crucial role in English as a second language (ESL) and English as a foreign language (EFRL). In Wilkins, Hassannejad (2015), it says, "If you don't speak the vocabulary you use, you won't have much worth creating grammatical phrases Vocabulary is one of the language elements that the students wanted to understand. Vocabulary learning plays an important role for second-language students. Earle W. Brockman (1997:1) Once a student has mastered the basic grammatical structures of a language, he will have the next challenge of mastering his or her vocabulary. In no language is someone ever learning all the words. From the statement above, the researcher may infer that vocabulary is extremely important to all, as you can make sentences, convey your emotions, contact each other etc.

Ideally, seventh-grade students will master a vocabulary list as recommended in the curriculum. Indeed, SMP Negeri 2 Kulo graduate students are not yet able to speak in vocabulary. Students seldom use their vocabulary in their work. It made it difficult for students to learn English, so the master's vocabulary is not yet adequate. Their poor mastery of speech therefore made it difficult for them to clearly understand English. This disorder makes it difficult for them to comprehend words in a sense and to have inadequate words to say. Most of SMP Negeri 2 Kulo students in their seventh grade were not interested in English. It revealed that when the researcher assigned the students to memorize five vocabulary, the student felt depressed by vocabulary. Then the researcher tries to ask what a basic vocabulary is for, but it is difficult for the student to respond to the meaning. The definition of a recitation is the accounting of facts or the act of saying something loudly memorized or read. Moreover, recitation is a public declaration of something that has been memorized. In addition, recitation or recitation, particularly formal or public, of something from memory. The student has to memorize vocabulary in recitative form. Specifying the details or memories is the capacity to remember. The recitative approach has been used to align all brain functions in process knowledge so that information can quickly be interpreted and memorized. In the recitative process, students are provided and are

asked to memorize lists of the target language terms with their mother tongue equivalents. They build phrases in which new words are used, to demonstrate that students understand the meaning and usage of a new vocabulary item. The student has the right to memorize several vocabulary to learn vocabulary in this way. Based on the above factors, the researchers are interested in studying the research under the title: "The efficacy of the recital method for improving students' vocabulary in SMP Negeri 2 Kulo's seventh grade degree." The researcher hopes to develop the mastery of vocabulary and to offer importance to students of every classroom form.

METHODS

Population and Sample

In this research, the population of this research is the students at seventh grade of SMP Negeri 2 Kulo. It consists of three classes and each class consists of 20 students. The total number of the students are 60 students.

In this research the sample is taken randomly. The researcher applied probability sampling with cluster sampling technique. The class is selected with cluster sampling technique because the class was big, so the researcher chooses one class as sample. This class is VII.2 which consists of 20 students.

Instrument of the Research

The instrument used in this research is an objective test. The test is the students memorizing vocabulary. The test aims at finding students' vocabulary mastery using a recitative method. The test uses pre-test and post-test. The pre-test aims to measure prior vocabulary mastery of the students. The post-test aims to find out the effectiveness of using a recitative method in students' achievement in vocabulary mastery.

Procedure of Collecting Data

The data of the study is obtained by using a type of test, which uses a memorizing test. The procedure of collecting data would be presented in chronological order as follows:

1. Pre-test

A pre-test is administered to assess the student's prior knowledge. In this section, the researcher gives an assignment to the students to mention and write much vocabulary based on their knowledge.

2. Post-test

The post-test is given after doing treatment. The content of the post-test is the same as the pre-test. The aim of the post-test is to know the student's vocabulary achievement after giving the treatment.

Treatment procedures

The treatment is conducted after the pre-test given in the classroom. The procedure of giving treatment is as follows:

- a) In first meeting, the researcher would give short explanation about vocabulary include definition of vocabulary, some of types vocabulary, vocabulary improvement in context.
- b) In the second meeting, before applies the treatment, the researcher would give some questions and asks the students to answer it. And then, gives some vocabularies about descriptive adjectives to memorized by the students.
- c) In the third meeting, the researcher would give question to the students about vocabulary that memorized in previous meeting and write the vocabulary with the meaning's. Then gives vocabulary about numeral adjectives to memorized by the students as a test in next meeting.
- d) In the fourth meeting, the researcher uses similary step as in third meeting.

RESULTS

Findings

The findings of this research deal with the students' score of pre-test and post-test, the mean score and standard deviation of pre-test and post-test. This findings are described as follows:

1. Students' vocabulary mastery

a. Scoring classification of students' test

Before and after giving a test, the researcher analyzed the students' score of one class (pre-test and post-test). The scoring classification of the students score is presented in table 1:

Table 1 The classification of scoring students' pre-test and post-test

No	Classification	Score	Pre-test		Post-test	
			F	%	F	%
1	Very Good	8,6 - 10	0	0	2	10,0
2	Good	7,1 - 8,5	2	10,0	12	60,0
3	Fairly	5,6 - 7,0	3	15,0	5	25,0
4	Poor	4,1 - 5,5	11	55,0	1	5,0
5	Very Poor	≤ 4,0	4	20,0	0	0
Sum			20	100,0	20	100,0

The table above shows that the students' score in pre-test and post-test. The result for pre-test shows that there is no student classified into very good, 2 students (10,0 %) classified into good, 3 students (15,0 %) classified into fairly, 11 students (55,0 %) classified into poor , and 4 students (20,0 %) classified into very poor. While the result for post-test shows that there are 2 students (10,0 %) classified into very good, 12 students (60,0 %) classified into good, 5 students (25,0 %) classified into fairly, 1 student (5,0 %) classified into poor, and there is no student classified into very poor. It means that the students' vocabulary mastery can improve beacuse most of the students score is increase. It shows that the students vocabulary mastery is higher after learning English by using recitative method.

b. The mean score and standard deviation of students' test result

After classifying the students vocabulary mastery, the mean score and the standard deviation of pre-test and post-test are presented in the following table:

Table 2 Mean score and Standard deviation of the students

Class VII.1	Mean Score	Standard Deviation
Pre-Test	49.70	13.28
Post-Test	73.50	11.33

Table 2 showed tat the mean score of the students in the post-test (73.50) was greater than pre-test (49.70). It meant the students who taught by using recitative method in improve students vocabulary mastery was better then students who not taught by using recitative method in improved students vocabulary mastery. The standard deviation of pre-test is 13.28 and standard deviation of post-test is 11.33. It means there is a significant different between students' pre-test and post-test. To prove it, the researcher applied independent t-test analysis using SPSS version 21.0.

c. Probablity Value (p-value)

The hypothesis stated was tested by using inferential analysis. In this case, the researcher applied paired samples t-test analysis using SPSS 21.0 program for Windows Evaluation Version. The purpose was to know whether or not the difference between the result of the students mean score pre-test and post-test. The result of calculating was shown as follow:

Table 3 P-Value of Students Speaking

α	P-Value
0.05	0.000

Based on the students result obtained and stated in findings above, the researcher used paired samples t-test in inferential statistic through SPSS 21.0 program for Windows Evaluation Version to test the hypothesis. In pre-test and post-test, the researcher found that the p-value was lower than the α ($0.000 < 0,05$).

d. Hypothesis

After applying p-value for the sample in calculating difference of the students' vocabulary mastery in pre-test and post-test is found that the p-value (0,000) is lower than the α (0,05). It means that H_0 was rejected and H_1 accepted. It can conclude that the students who were taught bay using recitative method were better than the students who taught by conventional way. Teaching vocabulary using recitative method has a good effect to students vocabulary mastery.

Discussion

The use of recitative techniques as a meditation instructor has contributed to the student's mastery of vocabulary. How students develop their vocabulary is worth exploring here. Most students found it hard to answer the question of the test when the pre-test was issued. You just guessed the best answer to choose, and

some of them robbed the work of their peers. It's a recet and lack of vocabulary because you have no previous knowledge of the subject in this situation.

The explanation of the data obtained by the test in the preceding section shows that the vocabulary mastery of the students substantially improves. The average score for students in class VII.2 is sponsored (post-test). The average after-test score is 73.50 higher then 49.70. The data showed that using a recitative approach is more powerful than using survey games when teaching vocabulary. The various mean score os pre-test and post-test is sponsored.

On the other hand, the researchers considered the p-value to be lower than α ($0,000 < 0,05$) based on the findings of the data analysis in Table 3 in the significance test. It means the rejection of H0 and the approval of H1 at a substantial level of α 0.05. It showed that the use of recitative approaches to teach vocabulary has the positive impact on students' mastery.

In terms of the description above, the investigator considers that vocabulary mastering is the highest score. To support this argument in Wahyuni (2012), the student must always learning words as they learn the structure and the practice of a sonic method," says Edward, who says vocabulary is an important factor in all language teaching." If the learner has ample vocabulary, he or she would be able to understand the words, speak fluently, and will easily understand the text's content. The vocabulary is used to describe the total number of words in the language of the Hornby in Sari (2007).

It is recitative to say information or the act of saying something loudly recalled or read. Moreover, recitation is a public declaration of something that has been memorized. The students are asked to memorize the recitative approach by presenting a list of the target language vocabulary and their native language equivalents. The student has the right to memorize several vocabulary to learn vocabulary. Students may write the words in the phrases.

Data from the scientist shows that recitative methods considerably round the vocabulary of students. The use of recitative methods in vocabulary learning makes the use of traditional method for students more successful. Research to develop vocabulary through a Reciprocal Lehrastrategy has been conducted in line with Ahmadi (2012:11). The textbook will help to improve vocabulary and to concentrate on the words required for each lesson in the textbooks of the student. In the analysis of lessons in various processes, students will use the new vocabulary, forecast, ask, explain and summarize.

On the basis of the above findings, the investigator found that recitational methods could improve the vocabulary of students.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Adel M. Alharbi.2015.*Building Vocabulary for Language Learning : Approach for ESL Learners to Study New Vocanulary*.journal, University of Memphis (USA).
- Ahmadi Mohammad Reza.2012.*Improving Vocabulary Learning in Foreign Language Learning Through Reciprocal Teaching Strategy* (journal).Penang,Malaysia : Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM).

- Ali Sorayaie Azar. 2012. *The Effect of Games on EFL Learners' Vocabulary Learning Strategies*.journal.English Department, Maragheh Branch-Islamic Azad University, Maragheh, Iran.
- Al-Khasawneh Fadi Maher and Huwari Ibrahim Fathi.2014.*The Effect of Metacognitive Strategies Instruction on Vocabulary Learning among Jordanian University Students* (journal).Malaysia:Northern University.
- ALLEN, French, (1983). *Techniques in teaching vocabulary*. Oxford: University Press.
- Anonim. *The Secret of Remembering: How to Trick Your Brain Into Memorizing Things*.Hofstra University.
- Armstrong Eric.2010.*Memorization and Practice* (journal).York University.
- Azhar Musarat et al.2014.*Notions of Vocabulary Learning Among The Students of University of Sargodha* (journal).Pakistan:University of Sargodha.
- Clouston Michael Lessard. *Challenging Student Approaches to ESL Vocabulary Development*.
- Hasannejad Mohammad Reza.2015.*Powerful Vocabulary Acquisition through Texts Comparison* (journal). Iranshahr, Iran: Islamic Azad University.
- [http:// www.interventioncentral.org](http://www.interventioncentral.org), 2 april 2016.
- http://www.academicjournals.org/article/article1379328836_Nemati.pdf, 2 april 2016.
- https://brocku.ca/MeadProject/Dewey/Dewey_1910a/Dewey_1910_o.html, 2 april 2016.02.49 pm.
- [http://rahmatsolihien.blogspot.co.id/2013/03/makalah-bahasa-inggris vocabulary.html](http://rahmatsolihien.blogspot.co.id/2013/03/makalah-bahasa-inggris-vocabulary.html). 2 april 2016.
- Irawan Haru.2011. *Using Picture-Based Story Telling Technique To Improve The Speaking Skill Of The Eleventh Graders Of MAN Kisaran* (Thesis).Malang:State University of Malang.
- Judy K. Montgomery. 2007. *The Bridge of Vocabulary: Evidence Based Activities for Academic Success (NCS Pearson Inc)*.
- Misrah Fadillah. 2011. *The Effectiveness of Teaching Vocabulary Through Total Physical Response*.skripsi.UIN Jakarta.
- Mofareh Alqahtani. 2015.*The importance of vocabulary in language learning and how to be taught*.journal.King Khaled Academy, Saudi Arabia.
- Mohammad Reza Ahmadi.2012. *Improving Vocabulary Learning in Foreign Language Learning Through Reciprocal Teaching Strategy*.journal.School of Educational Studies,Universiti Sains Malaysia.
- Nation Paul.2011.*Teaching Vocabulary* (journal). Wellington, New Zealand: Victoria University.
- Nation.2001.*Learning Vocabulary In Another Language*.United Kingdom:Cambridge University.

- Nemati Azadeh. 2009. *Memory vocabulary learning strategies and long-term* (journal).Karnataka State,India:University of Mysore.
- Nikita Nathan.2013.*Structuring Vocabulary for Tenderfoots*.Bhopal:Bansal Institute of Science and Technology.
- Rui Guo.2010.*Applying Incidental Learning to Vocabulary Memorization* (journal). Kristianstad University.
- Sari Komala.2007.*Teaching Vocabulary Through Contextual Clues*.Jakarta Selatan:State Islamic University.
- Sulistiyowati Lilis.2010.*The effectiveness of Teaching Vocabulary Using Hyponymy games* (Skripsi).Jakarta: State Islamic University.
- Touran Ahour & Parisa Salamzadeh. 2014. *Vocabulary Learning Strategies Used by Poor Iranian High School Students*.
- Umam Khoirul.2010.*Improving Students' Vocabulary Mastery with the Jakarta Post Newspaper Article*.Jakarta:State Islamic University.
- Ur Penny.2009.*A Course in Language Teaching Practice and Theory*.United Kingdom:Cambridge University Press.
- Wahyuni Sri.2012.*Memorizing Vocabulary by Using Picture Media at Class VIII* (Proposal).
- Yulia Mawaddah.2010.*Using Games in Teaching Vocabulary* (Skripsi).Jakarta Selatan:State Islamic University.
- Zamzam Emhemmad Mari Al-Dersi. 2013. *The Use of Short-Stories for Developing Vocabulary of EFL Learners*.journal.Department of English Language & Translation Studies, The Faculty of Arts, the University of Sebha,Sebha, Libya.
- Asrifan, A. (2009). Using songs in teaching English language for the young learners. ParePare: unpublished.
- Puasa, K., Asrifan, A., & Chen, Y. (2017). Classroom Talk in Bilingual Class Interaction. *Research in Pedagogy*, 7(1), 106-121.
- Nadirah, N., Tahir, M. H., & Asrifan, A. (2019). THE ABILITY TO TRANSLATE ENGLISH PHRASES INTO INDONESIAN AND THE DIFFICULTIES FACED BY THE ELEVENTH GRADE STUDENTS OF SMAN 1 PANCARIJANG. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 2(1), 41-46.
- Apdy, A. P. R., & Asrifan, A. (2019, April). The Chinese mime game in teaching vocabulary on EFL classroom. In *PROCEEDINGS OF THE 65th TEFLIN INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE* (Vol. 65, No. 01).
- Taslim, T., Asrifan, A., Chen, Y., & Nurdania, N. R. (2019). CORRELATION BETWEEN STUDENT'S VOCABULARY MASTERY AND SPEAKING SKILL. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 2(2), 65-76.
- Muthmainnah, M., Asrifan, A., Al Yakin, A., & Sahabuddin, C. (2019, April). The use of dictogloss technique on ELT classroom: An experiment study of students listening comprehension. In *PROCEEDINGS OF*

THE 65th TEFLIN INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE (Vol. 65, No. 01).

- Mutmainnah, M., Azis, S., Maulidya, U., & Asrifan, A. (2017). Glory Style in Mandar Song Lyrics: A study of Mandar Tribe in South Sulawesi, Indonesia. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCES IN LINGUISTICS*, 8(1), 1286-1291.
- Asrifan, A., Rinantanti, Y., Tang, S., & Nadirah, N. (2019). THE 3-DIMENSION PICTURES IN INCREASING THE STUDENTS ABILITY AND INTEREST TO WRITE DESCRIPTIVE COMPOSITION. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 2(1), 19-30.
- Asrifan, A., Nadira, N., & Haedar, H. (2018). IMPROVING STUDENTS'READING COMPREHENSION OF DESCRIPTIVE TEXT THROUGH COLLABORATIVE MURDER. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 1(2), 21-31.
- Asrifan, A. (2015). Analysis of English Students' Learning Style in Bilingual Class. *International Journal of Literature and Arts*, 3(4), 34.
- Farahdiba, S., & Asrifan, A. (2016). Speaking Ability and Psychological Barriers of the Second Year Students of Hotel Department of SMKN 1 Sidenreng Kabupaten Sidrap in Speaking English. *Asian EFL Journal*, (89), 41.
- Asrifan, A. (2012). Increasing the Students Ability to Write Descriptive Composition at SMP Negeri 13 Parepare by using the 3-Dimension Pictures.
- Tang, S., Asrifan, A., Chen, Y., Haedar, H., & Agussalim, M. (2019). THE HUMOR STORY IN TEACHING READING COMPREHENSION. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 2(2), 77-87.
- Nurwanti, N., Asrifan, A., & Haedar, H. (2019). THE APPLICATION OF COOPERATIVE LEARNING: JIGSAW II TECHNIQUE IN IMPROVING STUDENTS'READING COMPREHENSION OF EXPOSITORY TEXT. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 2(1), 31-40.
- Asrifan, A. (2016). The Effectiveness of Think-Pair-Share Technique in Improving Students' Speaking Ability and Interest. *English Literature and Language Review*, 2(3), 24-35.
- Asrifan, A., Muthmainnah, M., Al-Yakin, A., Sahabuddin, C., & Haedar, H. (2018). THE CAUSE-EFFECT TECHNIQUE IN TEACHING RECOUNT WRITING. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 1(2), 63-72.
- Asrifan, A., Vargheese, K. J., Syamsu, T., & Amir, M. (2020). ESP COURSE DESIGN: THE NEED ANALYSIS ON TOURISM DEPARTMENT IN INDONESIA VOCATIONAL HIGH SCHOOLS. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 3(2), 69-77.
- Asrifan, A., Ghofur, A., & Azizah, N. (2020). Cheating Behavior in EFL Classroom (A Case Study at Elementary School in Sidenreng Rappang Regency). *OKARA: Jurnal Bahasa dan Sastra*, 14(2), 279-297.

- Nadirah, N., Asrifan, A., Vargheese, K. J., & Haedar, H. (2020). INTERACTIVE MULTIMEDIA IN EFL CLASSROOM: A STUDY OF TEACHING READING COMPREHENSION AT JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL IN INDONESIA. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 3(2), 131-145.
- Muthmainnah, A. R., Atmowardoyo, H., Salija, K., & Asrifan, A. (2020). Literary Work as Teaching Materials: A Study of Students and Lecturers Needs Analysis. *Solid State Technology*, 63(5), 394-407.
- Tilome, A. A., Agustang, A., Jasruddin, M. S., & Asrifan, A. (2020). Social Exchange of Political Elites in the Regional Leader Election of Gorontalo Province, Indonesia. *Solid State Technology*, 63(5), 521-531.
- Pacinongi, A., & Asrifan, A. (2020). Bimbingan Pengawas Berkelanjutan dalam Mewujudkan Pendidikan Karakter Bangsa dalam Kegiatan Belajar Mengajar Penjaskes. *Celebes Education Review*, 2(1), 1-7.
- Gunawan, G., & Asrifan, A. (2020). Penerapan Kerja Kelompok Kegiatan MGMP Guru Ekonomi dalam Menyusun RPP untuk Meningkatkan Kompetensi Pedagogik. *Celebes Education Review*, 2(1), 31-36.
- Yusuf, I., & Asrifan, A. PENINGKATAN AKTIVITAS KOLABORASI PEMBELAJARAN FISIKA MELALUI PENDEKATAN STEM DENGAN PURWARUPA PADA SISWA KELAS XI IPA SMAN 5 YOGYAKARTA. Editorial Team, 32.
- Al Yakin, A., Sahabuddin, C., Rahayu, A., Fitriah, N., & Arifin, M. (2020). Political Celebrification and Electability: A Study of Political Phenomena Imaging in Election Polewali Mandar District, West Sulawesi, Indonesia. *Solid State Technology*, 63(5), 632-646.
- Junaedah, S. B. T., & Ahmad, M. A. (2020). The Outdoor Learning Modules Based on Traditional Games in Improving Prosocial Behaviour of Early Childhood. *International Education Studies*, 13(10).
- Octoberlina, L. R., & Muslimin, A. I. (2020). Efl students perspective towards online learning barriers and alternatives using moodle/google classroom during covid-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 9(6), 1-9.
- Octoberlina, L. R., & Anggarini, I. F. (2020). Teaching vocabulary through picture cards in Islamic Elementary School: a case study in Nida Suksa School, Thailand. *Jurnal Madrasah*, 13(1), 26-38.
- Octoberlina, L. R. (2016). Plagiarism in English language theses in Indonesia. *Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan*, 14(3).
- Octoberlina, L. R., & Anggarini, I. F. (2020). Teaching vocabulary through picture cards in Islamic Elementary School: a case study in Nida Suksa School, Thailand. *Jurnal Madrasah*, 13(1), 26-38.
- Asrifan, A., Zita, C. T., Vargheese, K. J., Syamsu, T., & Amir, M. (2020). THE EFFECTS OF CALL (COMPUTER ASSISTED LANGUAGE LEARNING) TOWARD THE STUDENTS' ENGLISH ACHIEVEMENT AND ATTITUDE. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED ENGLISH STUDIES*, 3(2), 94-106.

- Asrifan, A. (2021). ACADEMIC WRITING. LawArXiv. January, 2. <https://doi.org/10.31228/osf.io/x2s7e>
- Asrifan, A. (2020). TUTORIAL PENGGUNAAN QUIZIZZ (www. quizizz. com) PADA PEMBELAJARAN. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/kgnza>
- Asrifan, A. (2021). Abd Ghofur.“. THE USE OF READING CIRCLES IN INCREASING STUDENTS SPEAKING ABILITY AT THE ELEVENTH GRADE SMK NEGERI, 1. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/8vjxy>
- Asrifan, A. (2020). Pandemic, Humanity and Education. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/q2gpk>
- Asrifan, A. (2021). USING CAT AND MOUSE GAME TO IMPROVE STUDENT’S SPEAKING ABILITY AT THE ELEVENTH GRADE OF MA YMPI RAPPANG. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/phtvn>
- Asrifan, A., & Ghofur, A. (2021). THE USE OF READING CIRCLES IN INCREASING STUDENTS SPEAKING ABILITY AT THE ELEVENTH GRADE SMK NEGERI 1 PANCARIJANG. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/8vjxy>
- Asrifan, A. (2021). Book Review: Halliday. 1989. Spoken and Written Language. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ej8tb>
- Asrifan, A., & Ghofur, A. (2021). TALK, ACTION, SILENCE, INTERRUPTION AND THEIR IMPLICATIONS IN BUGINESE SOCIETY (SOPPENG REGENCY). <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/pv3ku>
- Asrifan, A. (2020). PENILAIAN BERBASIS ANDROID MENGGUNAKAN APLIKASI PLICKERS. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/htreq>